

Social Marketing - Present Scenario

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Seetha, V & Lavanya, A. "Social Marketing - Present Scenario." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 89–95.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461444>

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Abstract

Social Marketing, being a social and managerial process, must have a social, environmental approach. Unfortunately very few business organizations cared for it. Social marketing came as a separate discipline in the 1970's as a result of the acceptance of the environmental approach by the western countries. Nowadays, social marketing principles are being used in developing countries in areas such as health promotion, population control environment conservation, economic development, racism and human rights. Social marketing is not a new phenomenon as its roots can be seen in development strategies, social reform campaigns in olden days. In ancient Greece and Rome anti-slavery campaigns were launched. During industrial revolution period, campaigns were launched to grant voting rights to woman and abolition of child labor notable social reform movements, such as abolition of Sati (self-immolation) system, abolition untouchability, prevention of child marriages, woman education, etc. This study is of descriptive covers secondary data relating to social marketing issues.

Introduction

Marketing, being a social and managerial process, it must have a social, environmental approach. Unfortunately, very few business organizations cared for it. Social Marketing came into being as a separate discipline as a result of the acceptance of the environmental approach by the Western countries. Nowadays, social marketing principles are being used in developing countries in areas such as health promotion, population control, environment conservation, economic development, racism and human rights. Social Marketing is not a new phenomenon as its roots can be seen in development strategies, social reform campaigns in olden days. In ancient Greece and Rome anti-slavery campaigns were launched. During the industrial revolution period, campaigns were launched to grant voting rights to woman and abolition of child labor in Great Britain. Notable social reforms movements, such as the abolition of Sati (Self-immolation) system, the abolition of untouchability, prevention of child marriages, woman education, etc. were successfully organized during Pee-independence era in India.

Concept of Social Marketing

Social Marketing is a process of changing behavior and attitudes of the public (Target group) for achieving social, economical, political and business objectives. Social Marketing refers to the development of awareness among consumers, organizations (i.e., social, political, business, etc.) and the general public regarding the long-term interests of the business world. Philip Kotler and Gerald Zaltman defined social marketing as “ the design, implementation and control of programmes calculated to influence the acceptability of social ideas and to involve considerations of product designing, pricing, communication, distribution and Marketing research.”

Commercial Marketing convinces consumers to buy different types of products and services on the same line; people can be convinced to adopt social marketing products such as health care, education or social reforms. Andreasen defines social Marketing as “the application of commercial Marketing technologies to the analysis’ planning, execution and evaluation of programmes designed to influence to the voluntary behavior of target audiences to improve their welfare and that of their society.”

Social Marketing is also referred to as societal Marketing. It aims at achieving the following

Objectives

- Satisfaction of Customer needs.
- Improvement of quality of life.
- Implementation of long-term policy for customers and society’s welfare.
- Freedom from all sorts of pollution and ecological destructions.

Aspects of Social Marketing

In recent years, the world community has realized the ill-effects of technological developments, industrialization, profit-oriented marketing and malaise supply of product (i.e., hazardous to health and environment). So that sociologists, the social leaders, the philanthropists and Marketers advocated social marketing. Over the past few years, marketing experts, practitioners have tried to identify basic aspects (component) of social marketing. These can be summarized as under:

- **Need-based and Eco-friendly product mix:** The social market product may be a physical product like contraceptives or services like health examination or ideas like environmental protection. The social marketer has to make the people ware about their needs, problems and then sell the need-based products of services and not merely sell the products that he is having. Social marketing products that he is having. Social marketing product must be essentially eco- friendly.
- **Rational Promotional Policy:** Social Marketing sells ideas, thoughts (i.e., Antodaya) attitudes and behaviors (i.e., Social, Religious, etc.) for the propose of promoting, social products, social marketer uses advertising media, public relations, door to door selling, public meetings, vehicles, distribution, of coupons, etc. Social Marketing emphasizes the adoption of the promotional policy by all organizations (i.e., social educational, business, etc.) The promotion of products/ services should not be anti-social, anti-ethics and anti-ecology.
- **Reasonable price of the Product:** The price of the social marketing product may be in the form of money, time, labor or the form of trouble (i.e., trouble after immunization)
- **The social marketer has to adopt a reasonable pricing policy** in which the benefits gained by the consumer are greater than the costs of the product. While making pricing decisions, he must consider factors such as the purchasing power of the target groups and the quality of the product. Too high or too lower prices of the products may get less or no response from the consumers. It has been observed that neglecting the interest of consumers, some

pharmaceutical companies and soft-drink manufacturing companies maintain a 400-500% profit margin on the cost of the product. Social marketing does not allow such type of exploitation.

- **Effective and efficient Distribution:** Social marketing products may be tangible (i.e., body building equipment), intangible ideas (i.e., spiritual development), services (i.e., transportation, communication, etc.) and practices (i.e., Morning walk, breast feeding, use of condoms, etc.) The social marketer has to provide social products to the customers at the right time and the right place so that they are benefited. The place of distribution should be well communicated and accessible to the consumers.
- **Partnership between organizations and society:** Social marketing aims at achieving long-term goals such as health promotion, production, population control, environmental conservation, etc. these issues are complex and require to combine efforts by various organizations (i.e., Govt. Organization, Non-Govt. Organizations, Educational Institutions, and other Social Organization) to give better results.
- **Suitable Govt. Policies:** Social marketing programmers may attract resistance from the targeted group. For example, the introduction of Sex education at school level is being opposed by parents in India. Social marketing seeks political support to implement controversial social issues such as prevention of child marriages, encouraging inter-cast marriages, population control, etc. many times political diplomacy is needed to gain the support of the target group. While implementing the social reform campaigns, the target group should be taken into confidence. This creates an environment suitable to behavioral changes required for social programmers.

Relevance of Social Marketing in India

The Indian society has been facing problems such as poverty, population explosion, illiteracy, lower Indian Journal of Marketing 17 capital formation and other social problems. The development strategies so far adopted resulted in degradation in social, cultural, environmental and health care, so the need of application of social marketing principles is felt urgently enrich the life Indian citizen. A research study has included that the industrial units situated in Champur. Mumbai, emit more than 111 tons of hazardous carbon dioxide daily. According to the observation of Centre of Science Environment, Delhi, of the total water reservoir in India, more than 70% water is polluted. The NEERI (National Environmental Engineering Institute, Nagpur) has shown that ill-habits of people result in 60% water pollution while industrialization is responsible for 40% water pollution in India. Due to consumption of polluted water, more than 15 lakh children die per year.

The major aluminum corporate in Orissa are the damaging environment and are responsible for the displacement of more than 2000 tribal families. 6 Out of 3119 cities in India, only 209 cities have sewage water treatment plants. The river Yamuna gets daily two crore liter of untreated water. Calcutta and Mumbai have noise above 80 decibels. Bhopal Gas Tragedy (1984) look victim of more than 2500 citizens, more than 40000 were handicapped and blind and still are suffering from various diseases. The ozone layer has been depleting because of pollution agents like chlorofluoro carbon and methyl chloroform emitted by cold storages, refrigerators and green houses. Due to this, we experience hot waves having the intensity of 45 to 500 c in our country.

The worst oil spill during the 1991 gulf war killed thousands of sea birds, fish and other aquatic lives. Deforestation is not only ruining the environment but causing an economic loss of Rs. 2.30 billion per year India. In Agra city, the pollution created by industries is ruining the beauty of the world famous 'Taj Mahal.' Deforestation in India is going on at a fast speed, running valuable flora and fauna coupled with an irreparable loss to the soil to soil. So the need of the hour is to protect the

environment from further loss. Business organizations, marketers, Govt. Organization and NGOs, social organizations must apply principles of social marketing to achieve their respective goals coupled with the goal of enriching mental, cultural and health facilitates. In India, social marketing principles are being used for achieving business as well as health care, population control, adult education, etc. Still, social marketing has a long to go to a developing country like India.

Prospects for Social Marketing

In the 21st Century Social Marketing principles could certainly benefit the organization (i.e., social, educational, health, political and business), the consumers and change the socio-economic and an environmental system, Information Technology has made communication systems very dynamic, interactive and effective. So the whole world has become a ‘Global Village.’

In the world of Marshal Goldsmith “new technologies, new organizations and the rise of global village will have a propound effect on our sense of community in the years ahead. Two trends stand out: the explosion of our potential to communicate instantaneously and massively across the globe and, closely aligned with our ability to create communities of our choice”⁸. In future social marketers will have to adopt information technology to build rapport with target groups, gaining the support of the masses to social reform campaigns, health promotion campaigns and creating awareness regarding environment protection for themselves and future generations.

Secondary Data

Secondary data means data that are already available (i.e.), they refer to the data which have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. In this study the secondary data is collected from books websites, journal, and magazines

Women’s Education in India

Women’s education in India plays a very important role in the overall development of the country. It not only helps in the development of half of the human resources but in improving the quality of life at home and outside. Educated women not only tend to promote the education of their girl children but also can provide better guidance to all their children. Moreover educated women can also help in the reduction of infant mortality rate and growth of the population.

- Educating the women will empower them to seek gender equality in the society.
- Women will be able to earn that would raise their economic condition and their status in the society.
- They will be aware of the advantages of small and planned family and this will be a big step towards achieving stabilized population goals.
- It has been reported that the single most important factor affecting high total fertility rates (TFR) is the low status of women in many societies. Women education will help increase the age of marriage of women and they would tend to have fewer, healthier children who would live longer.
- Women on being educated would be able to rear their children in a better way, leading to their good health and provide them with better facilities.

Child Marriage in India

Child marriage is one of the burning problems of Indian society. Generally, child marriage means a marriage of individuals who marry before the minimum legal age, which 18 years for girls & 21 years for boys. What convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) refers to child marriage is a marriage of a child younger than 18 years old. Child marriage occurs particularly in developing countries in Sub-Sahara Africa, Latin America, and South & South-East Asia. Almost half of the child marriages occur globally in South Asia. India is one of the countries in this region where girl child marriage is an unbending social problem.

As per the National Family Health Survey, a slight improvement occurs during last two decades in the prevalence on child marriage in India, but the fact is that the improvement occurs mainly in urban areas, the situation in rural India remains as it was. The incidence of child marriage in rural areas is alarming as it stands at 52% when compared to urban areas 28%. Data shows child marriage is common in India prevalence highest in Bihar, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, UP, MP, Chhattisgarh, AP & West Bengal. Child marriage has been practicing since ancient time. Its root was very deep in Indian society.

The evil practice is higher in rural areas. The socio-economic, cultural & educational factors are responsible for child marriage. The lack of awareness & inadequacy of laws is also encouraging this evil practice. Child marriage put the worst effect on society. It is a violation of children's rights where it deprives them of the basic right to health, nutrition, education & freedom.

Consequently, they are hardly suffering from violation, abuse & exploitation. Young married girls are often getting harassment physically, mentally & emotionally. The government of India has taken various steps to prohibit child marriage. In spite of, child marriage is practicing continuously in India. One-third of girls around the world become brides before the age of 18 and one in nine is married under the age of 15. The UN estimated that nearly 70 million women aged 20-24 around the world had been married before 18 years.

Voting Rights to Women

Women emerged as a distinct interest group in the 19th century primarily because of the bourgeoisie democratic revolutions of the 17th and 18th century that excluded women from their concept of equality. This distinction was based on gender. Since then women as a commune had waged a struggle for recognition of their rights as a human being. Women's execute multilateral role in the society, i.e., as a breadwinner of her family, as a care taker of her family as a mother, wife, daughter and service provider to the society.

In spite of the fact that the women's contribution to the country's development is equal to that of their male counterpart, still, they experience some limitations that restrain them from comprehending their potential for expansion. It was against this background that the government's all over the world felt the need to prioritize the interests of women and their participation at every stage of the development process. Women as a core group of concern emerged as a major theme in the Millennium Development Goal. The Millennium Development Goal is the eight goals set by the United Nations in 2000 which will act as a yardstick to determine the advancement in the direction of the obliteration of global poverty. UN stated that 'Gender Equality and Women Empowerment' as one of the Millennium Development Goals to be attained by the year 2015.

Child Labour

A full century. 100 years. Almost two generations of human lives. That is the timeline we are looking at. The timeline when, going by present trends, the menace of child labor in India might be ended.

Every year, thousands of innocent boys and girls are conscripted into bonded slavery. Every year, voices are raised against the enslaving of young children. And yet every year the traffic shows no discernible slack. India can lay claim to the gruesome feather in its hat of being the country with the highest number of child laborers in the World

Conclusion

Social marketing is being applied world over and India is no exception. This concept has altered the traditional concept of marketing. Society oriented development strategy can be helpful in overcoming the serious problems like pollutions explosion, ecological imbalance, the world over poverty, imbalanced development and meeting the basic needs, e.g., drinking water, food and shelter, education and health care. Social marketing can be applied in any sphere of life and can help in enriching the life of human being and care for the safety of the universe. The explosion of information technology made communication very dynamic. The leaders of social change will have to adopt information technology for communication is interacting and confidence building among masses. Let us hope that Indian development policies have the essence of social principles linked with nonpollution and ecology in the interest of present and future generations.

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